
Mutual Coordination of Business Law - Intellectual Property with Artificial Intelligence as The Most Effective Knowledge Solution for a Modern Market

Naumovski Ljupcho¹, Naumovska Simona²

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Abstract

Always, there is a general interest in life as a phenomenon that needs to be studied. But life is complex the fact that there is interest in "systems that demonstrate the phenomena of living systems", the nature of reproduction or solving the philosophical-psychological problems of self-awareness. The interest in artificial intelligence (AI) currently covers deeply relevant, acute everyday problems of humanity, which are in connection with the impending AI revolution. The Impact of the Revolutionary Age of Innovation from all points of view of the state, business, companies and the structure of employment is undoubtedly relevant. Artificial intelligence as one of the most advanced areas of research for scientists today allows text recognition; robots artificially replace human creative labor. The term "knowledge" is becoming increasingly active and used in computer science. The experts are on the attitude that the improvement on the so-called intelligent systems to search high level of information, systems for dialogue based on natural languages, interactive systems between man and machines (used and in management, design, scientific research) in big extent is determined how successful will be resolved problems through the presentation of knowledge.

¹ Doctor of business law and administration at *Private higher education institution- Euro College, Kumanovo, Republic of Macedonia*. Email: l_naumovski@yahoo.com

² *Private higher education institution- Euro College, Kumanovo, Republic of Macedonia*. Email: monaumovska@gmail.com

1. Introduction

"We are drowning in information but starved for knowledge"
(John Naisbitt, author of Megatrend)

Artificial intelligence (AI) - a revolutionary technology that is rapidly evolving, and its impact on all walks of life are already being felt. Strategic response measures require a serious real basis, which is designed to provide research in the field of technology development trends, dedicated to AI. Artificial intelligence is a new direction in digital technology and already has a profound impact on our world. This situation causes the rise of industrial, new socio-economic impacts that normally and realistically cause a boom in the styles of the production process and marketing of goods and services, and thus on our current way of life. Not to mention ahead of time, but the perception is de facto, AI certainly influence traditional concepts of intellectual property. Certainly, shortly soon AI will generate music and create new smart things, and thus will initiate changes in the terminology itself for the terms "composer", "author" and "inventor", but how? However let's leave it to time Implementation and use of artificial intelligence technologies will be reflected on policies and legislation, i.e. business law, and thus on IP systems around the world. Doing business internationally requires knowledge of the legal documents of many countries, as well as an understanding of cultural differences and therefore will that difficult. Humanity entered the era of "electronics", like what pointed from the founder of Microsoft Bill Gates, "and is in a situation yes generates thoughts and procedures". The development of new IT techniques gave a new impetus for technically imaginary progress and lead to the passage from civil society in the IT society (on knowledge base) phase of socio-economic development, forming a new today reality.

In this reality, the action and the image of many social organs and regulators, as and of the law, are violated. It is about not just a tool, a tool which provides an introduction of IT and its use in different fields of public life (economics, management and other segments from social life), but also hardens as an object to the impact from "the digitalization". The content, the form, the mechanism of the rule of law, and thus the law is changing. "Mental abilities needed for adjustment, as well as for shaping and selection on which any context is Intelligence" [Sternberg, Robert J., and Williams, Wendy M. \(1997\)](#).

In Webster's Dictionary: "Intelligence is: a) the ability to respond successfully to any particular situation by making appropriate behavioral adjustments; b) the ability to understand the connections between the facts of reality to develop actions that lead to the achievement of the goal" ([Webster-dictionary](#)).

Function enough labs, which through work activities of experts for computer creation, and have the ability to think identical, like one individual. Psychologists have created a model of the human mind/reason in the way of its own (human) thinking.

Mathematicians created it theory of algorithms, which became the foundation of the mathematical theory of calculation, while knowledge of the world is subordinated and structured, for resolving tasks with optimal calculations and with that are created and the first computers. The base of the system of the AI is shaping/designing cognitive programs for obtaining computer information, and for exclusively positive interaction of a man as an individual or a group of people, for a final solution of problems from different areas for which is need human intelligence.

Relevance of the topic. In the last decade, in connection with the development of the computer industry, there were ways to create a virtual rival for the human player, by effectively imitating conscious activity within of the solution of problems which they face in person. The existence of an atmosphere of competition requires various empirical tricks from the developers while artificial intelligence essentially works with the same concepts and methods as the scientific man who works

in the personal name. Today developers dedicate increasing attention to realism. Today the reality is that not only graphics, sound, but also computer-controlled behavior it becomes more and more similar to the behavior of real people. Much attention is paid to the development of artificial intelligence, by finding new algorithms, as well as SEO for improving existing ones, and which are time-tested. In view of the above, the task is creating information technology that provides architecture and a set of methods and algorithms, whose use will enable universalization of the process of creation of effective AI subsystems. The elaboration of artificial intelligence is related to the correct and successful implementation of knowledge according to and in the law framework (copyright). The subject of research - AI and its improvement in the use only within the law framework.

Purpose of the work: a man with his own activity through the labyrinth of knowledge enables the creation of artificial intelligence that will be necessary based on law. In the implemented work, an attempt is made to have - Introducing the reader to the real world of artificial intelligence; - Explore the promising areas in which artificial intelligence can be applied; - Law and artificial intelligence. The paper can be of interest to anyone interested in artificial intelligence, knowledge and law [Kevin D. Ashley \(2017\)](#).

Origin of the study. This study addresses issues arising from the development and implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) i.e. technologies. It also reviews the literary and technical frameworks of countries and regions around the world created for the study ([European Parliamentary Research Service, 2020](#)). It is in fact a comparison of human responsibility in the context of the middle; and certain implications of AI, as it relates to human relationships.

2. Materials and Methods

The basis is a complex of different methods of knowledge, research, description and explanation of the studied thematic horizon. The definitions and interpretations of the concept of "artificial intelligence", the descriptions of its essential characteristics are to some extent reflected in the works of the following Russian authors: L. Bolotov, T. Gavrilova, I. Ponkin, B. Ruchkin, D. Smolin, V. Fulin, L. Jasnitski. There are a number of translated publications on this topic, in particular - the authorship of Ethem Alpaydin, Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig, George George Luger, Alex M. Andrew, Earl Hunt, Patrick Henry Winston, Nils Nilsson, Stephen Hawking, Roger Penrose, Abner Shimony and Nancy Cartwright, Nick Bostroma. The same issues are reflected in the works of the following foreign authors: George F. Luger, Daniel Castro and Joshua New, Joost N. Kok, Egbert J. W. Boers, Walter A. Kosters, Peter van der Putten, Robert S. Engelmores, Nils J. Nilsson, Michael Guihot, Anne F. Matthew, Nicolas Suzor, Raymond Kurzweil, Elaine Rich, Kevin Knight, Shivashankar B. Nair, Richard Bellman, James R. Slagle, Stuart J. Russell, Peter Norvig, Edwina L. Rissland, Kevin D. Ashley and Ronald Prescott Loui, Avneet Pannu, Ronal Chandra, Yoga Prihastomo, Andrew Haskins, Surabhi Arora, Uttara Nilawar, Pei Wang, Earl B. Hunt, Patrick Henry Winston, Nick Bostrom, Irving John Good. From foreign authors who wrote about general legal aspects of the phenomenon of artificial intelligence and the legal aspects of its ontology (being), we consider it necessary to designate the following: Jurgita Grigienė, Gintarė Sirbikytė, Nicolas Petit, Jessica S. Allain, João Paulo de Almeida Lenardon, Matthew U. Scherer, Adam Thierer, Andrea Castillo, Simon Arcus, Bruce McClintock, Ryan Calo, Erica Palmerini. "The right of robots" is reflected in the works of the following foreign authors: Hervé Jacquemin, Jean-Benoît Hubin, Aïda Ponce Del Castillo, Ugo Pagallo, Ronald Leenes, Federica Lucivero, Alain Bensoussan, Jérémy Bensoussan, Ian Kerr, Neil M. Richards, William D. Smart, Sergio Saiz, E. Aristova, [Arkhipov, V, & Naumov, V. \(2017\)](#).

The method of scientific analysis (system analysis method and special analytical methods) to perceive the main segments on the thematic horizon being studied, conceptualization, perception oriented towards Megan Ewell (at a basic level of understanding). The method of induction (from specific to general) separation of conclusions and estimates of the studied phenomena, processes, correlations. The method of deduction allows passage from general research to concepts of artificial intelligence, peculiarities and design production, programming, sales, application (activation), operation, elimination of artificial intelligence units, risks and uncertainties related to this - to study such features already within the framework of intellectual property law. They were involved a number of research methods: legal, formal (which enable the presentation of the appropriate content of the studied acts and rules), comparative legal (which allow identifying differences in approaches currently implemented in different countries), legal and teleological (which make it possible to understand current and promising goals aimed at legislation in the field of research, etc.

3. Results and Discussions

The fundamental tasks of the AI system have always been to motivate the realization of new technologies and creative works and sustainability of the economy/business. From a business point of view, if the other goals of the AI system are not taken into account, such as providing "deserved incentive" and protection of moral rights, then why not use AI to stimulate inventions or creative works generated by artificial intelligence. However, precise answers are not yet available. The breadth of the use of AI technologies will cause a change in the terminology developed in AI: patents, industrial models, literary and artistic works, etc. The reality is that this is already happening, and the reason is not only AI but also specifically the digital economy. For example, in the medical-biological sciences, huge amounts of data of significant value are stored, but inventions are not (in the classical sense of the word). All this causes the determination of rights and obligations that are attached to them.

Knowledge as a foundation

We have to remember that science is not only an organism of knowledge but also a direction of knowledge. Every day you self we ask ourselves - when people started thinking about artificial intelligence, where did it start the accumulation of knowledge in the field of this really a "hot" topic? The beginnings of the idea for the re-creation of the human mind appeared even before inventing the first electronic computers in the first half of the 20th century. In 1637, in his work "Discourse on Method," Rene Descartes put forward a mechanistic theory that a universe is a giant machine, and that humans and animals are complex mechanisms comparable to clocks [Descartes, R. \(2013\)](#).

After that, in 1640, Thomas Hobbes, in his Treatise - Human Nature stopped in defiance of mechanical determinism in relation to human nature. The mechanical theory was followed by William Harvey, who discovered the circulatory system. (From the point of view of mechanics, the heart is a pump that pumps blood without the participation of the soul), Galileo Galilei, Robert Hooke, Robert Boyle, Isaac Newton and many other famous light minds. Such thoughts became widespread as a result of the technological advances that took place in Europe during those years. In 1623, Wilhelm Schickard developed a model of the first six-digit mechanical "computer" apparatus, then called the "counting clock", and performed simple mathematical functions such as adding, multiplying, dividing, and subtracting numbers [Guter, S.R. & Polunov, L. Yu. \(1981\)](#).

The popularity of technology has made scientists look like living organisms in relation to mechanics. The discovery of the "mechanism" in organisms gives an understanding of artificial intelligence in the most primitive sense. The invention of the machine from Schickard was followed

by the creation in 1643 by Blaise Pascal on a summation machine that performed arithmetic operations on 5-digit numbers, and in 1673 by Gottfried Wilhelm von Leibniz a calculating machine capable of multiplication and division operations. In 1832 [Korsakov, S.N. \(2009\)](#) set out the principle of development of scientific methods and enhancement devices of the possibilities of the mind, directly drawing analogies between his machines as an improvement of the possibilities of the mind, same as what a telescope or the microscope improves vision capabilities, and presented a series of five "intelligent machines" invented by him for mechanized information processing for data retrieval, comparison and classification tasks. For the first time in the history of computer science, Korsakov used punched cards in the design of his machines. Perforated cards acted as a kind of "knowledge base", and the "intelligent machines" themselves were the forerunners of modern professional systems. Korsakov's work contains a whole galaxy of new ideas of the time, such as: searching for multiple criteria taking into account the relative importance of different criteria (weighting coefficients), method of processing large data sets, the forerunner of modern expert systems, an attempt to define the concept of an algorithm ([Trogemann, Georg, Wolfgang Ernst, & Nitussov, Y.A., 2001](#)).

In 1928, the German mathematician David Hilbert turned the world's attention to problem-solving (Entscheidungsproblem (entscheidungsproblem-decision-problem): does it exist procedure with which it can be determined whether a statement is proven, or still some statements are possible (such as include mathematical puzzles such as Fermat's last theorem, assumption of Goldbach or Kolac's assumption) destined to remain unresolved? He simply said, "There is no unsolvable problem." You only need to find an algorithm that would you accept as input description of any problem by solving (formal language and mathematical statement "S" in this language) - and, after a final number of steps, will stop and give one of two answers: "True" or "False" - depending on whether the statement "S" is true or false ([Edelman, S. L, 1975](#)).

In 1936, Alan Turing, who now is considered the founder of AI theory, and the American mathematician and logician Alonzo Church, independently one from another made a statement that there is no algorithm that solves the problem of the resolution, i.e. impossibility for the existence of a formal, purely mechanical procedure which will allow deciding whether the given statement can be subtracted from a set of mathematical axioms, now known as The Church-Turing Theorem ([Turing, Alan M., 2013](#)).

In his article "On Computational Numbers, Using the Problem of Determination", Turing developed a concept of an abstract digital computer to solve this problem, which was later renamed the "Turing Machine", capable of imitating (if appropriate) any machine whose action is a transfer from one to another discrete state ([Turing, Alan M., 1973](#)).

This was the first attempt to automate logical and mathematical calculations, which at that time could only be performed by humans. In his next article, "Computer Machines and the Mind", published in the journal „Mind“, Turing exhibited a thought experiment (later called the Turing test), which consisted of the fact that two persons, man and woman, through a channel that excludes it voice perception, communicate with third-person separated from them by a wall, which tries to determine the gender of each from his interlocutors using indirect questions; while the man trying to confuse him the questionnaire, and the woman helps him to the questioner to discover the truth. The question is whether the machine will be able to participate so successfully in this "Imitation". Still, in 1950, the question arises: "Can the machine think?" or, even more precisely, "Can the machine? Respectively to communicate with a face in natural language? ([Turing, M. Alan, 1950](#)).

The Renaissance (Greek tradition), give impetus to progress a more powerful view of humanity and its role in nature. Empiricism replaced mysticism as a means of explaining the universe. Clocks (and hence factory layouts) have replaced the rhythm of nature for thousands of city dwellers. Most

modern social and physical theories are rooted in the idea of the possibility of analyzing mathematical activities and results and the intelligibility of natural or artificial movements. In particular, scientists and philosophers realized that thinking by itself, as a way of presenting knowledge, is heavy, but a fundamental subject for scientific study. Naturally is to strive for computer representation of knowledge. A computer is an intermediary tool in human cognitive activity. The computer, as well as other intermediary instruments (household tools and objects, devices, sign-symbol systems, etc.), is a means of objectifying the accumulated knowledge, the embodiment of socio-historical experience and activities. Theoretical-cognitive role as a result of a person's choice of decisions that are significant from the point of view of social practice becomes possible accurately with the help of mediation cases. "Computer," emphasizes [Acad. C. Pospelov](#) - is a tool for the intellectual activity of people, and the scientific direction "artificial intelligence" gives this tool new qualities and provides a new, more promising style of its use.

The level of representation of knowledge differs from the level of representation of data not only in a more complex structure but also for significant features: interpretation, the presence of classified links (for example, the relationship between knowledge related to a particular element and knowledge of this set), which allows the storage of information that is the same for all elements of the set, recorded in one act when describing the set itself, the presence of situational relations (simultaneity, being at one point in space, etc.), these relations determine it is situational compatibility of certain knowledge stored in memory). In addition, the level of knowledge is characterized by such signs as the presence of special generalization procedures, additional knowledge available in the system and a number of other procedures. which allows the storage of information that is the same for all elements of the set, recorded in one act when describing the set itself, the presence of situational relations (simultaneity, being at one point in space, etc.), these relations determine the compatibility of knowledge stored in memory). "Knowledge" means "to be aware", i.e. to "understand" one's intellectual quality ([vocabulary.com](#)). AI is currently the "loud word" in the industrial sector. The promotion of AI in a situation of equality with human being is a reality in the future.

In correlation of the computer apparatus with the brain of a human being, it is general for the developed equipment, because it works on what it "sees", i.e. on specially assigned tasks. AI has no consciousness in reality, so the abilities of human being are higher than AI. ([Verhezen, Peter 2019](#)).

Your Position, for the current analysis for super data and more specific devices for studying, is the results of narrow AI, which brings reasoned decisions. Realistically they are not yet able to realize rational, that is sound smart decisions. Realistically, will the capabilities of the human being with knowledge management (KM) dominate the uncertainty of what is a priority for us, humans, for a more sophisticated and comfortable living? But we will not dominate the computer in terms of data acquisition speed and classification, and when we speak for, creativity, innovation, then we are certainly more dominant. True living intelligence will be realized only when computers will be able to create and perceive what is relevant to the human being that is when we will have a real activation of the processing of "what". AI must properly realize causality, i.e. with counter activity. ([Sanzogni, L., Guzman, G., & Busch, P. 2017](#)).

It is realized colossal shares for constructiveness, for the codification of knowledge and the coverage of AI in knowledge management (KM). KM is a set of several sciences with the sole task of enabling the human potential and the organizations themselves to realize all kinds of economic and social relations based on the achieved knowledge. The correlation between KM and AI has the task of reaching cognitive computers that in reality will use models to enable processes of human thought, i.e. independent/deep learning, for text/data, determining the forms and their adaptation to the required language based on copying the human brain. This type of computer paves the way for future applications that include AI and KM.

Artificial Intelligence

Intelligence - (Latin *Intellectus* - knowledge, understanding, reason) - Accumulation of relevant facts, - enabled situation of studying novelties. - Adjustment for real satisfaction of the principles of the environment, i.e. mental principle in a person. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a special part of the science that deals with the differences in the exact copying of biological human intelligence, within which theories and models are built to explain and use the principles and mechanisms of human intellectual activity in technical systems. AI is part of computer science, for the development of software and hardware tools that enable the non-programmer user to set and solve their own, traditionally considered intellectual tasks, communication with a computer in a limited subset of natural language. In other words, in short, AI is the technical (informational and software and hardware) implementation of some human intellectual abilities. AI is a field of computer science that researches and automates intelligent behaviour. The intelligence of man is in constant correlation with finding solutions (actions, models) in new, non-standard situations. Intellectual activity is based on knowledge of the scientific branch with set tasks to solve.

Thinking with consciousness

Awareness is not so much a product of natural progress as a product of human social life, the social labor of previous generations of people. It is an essential part of human activity, through which human nature is created and it cannot be accepted outside of itself.

However if in machines reflection is passive, dead physical-chemical, mechanical act without generalization and penetration into the essence of the generalized phenomenon, then the reflection in the form of consciousness is "Knowledge of highly organized matter for oneself, penetration into the essence, natural law, objects and phenomena of objectivity." Reflection is not conscious in the machine because it is performed without the formation of ideal images and concepts, but occurs in the form of electrical impulses, signals, etc. So, according to our understanding, the machine does not think, this is not a form of reflection that takes place in the process of human knowledge of the surrounding world. The laws of reflection in the machine are conceptualized, above all, by the laws of reflection of reality in the mind of a person, because the machine is created by a person in order to reflect reality more accurately, and it is not the machine itself that reflects reality, but the person reflects it with the help of a machine. Therefore, the reflection of reality with a machine is an integral element of the reflection of reality by a person.

The advent of cyber devices does not lead to a new form of reflection, but to a new connection. Thinking is correlated with the realization, transmission and transformation of information as well as the processes that occur both in the brain, but and in other systems - the computers. For AI, understanding the relationship of thinking is sensation and the thinking creates a basis for obtaining a solution to the set task/problem. This correlation of thinking and other properties of matter derives from two fundamental principles: the principle of the material unity of the world and the principle of progress. But this relation cannot nor be absolutized nor be denied. Thinking is a human quality and is different from cyber information processing. Despite the qualitative non-identity of the machine and the brain in their functions, there are general patterns (command, communication and control) that are in the domain of AI. But this analogy of the activity of the automatic and nervous systems, even in terms of information processing, is relatively conditional and cannot be absolutized. In this connection, it should be noted that some of the studies of cybernetics, especially those conducted in the early period of its development, were characterized by mechanistic and

metaphysical tendencies. Actively respect for the qualitative differences of the artificial matter and the thinking brain in every line between the knowing subject and object of the material world it was erased.

Human consciousness and its relation to functioning AI devices

When we are differently inspired, we talk about the essence of human consciousness and its relation to the functioning of cyber devices. But, at present, the prospects for the development of cyber machines and their relationship to the human mind are being discussed. For to realize a machine that functions as a brain, it is necessary to create a substance with properties or similar to the highly organized protein substance that forms the brain. True, such a machine would function "like a brain," but it would not think. To think, the matter must exist not only in economic but also in social form. And replacing inorganic content with organic does not provide this, moreover, as a result of such replacement, one of the main advantages of the electronic machine will be lost. For the realization of AI, based on modelling, as thinking inanimate creatures, it is necessary to consider two aspects of this problem.

First, AI does not model all brain functions, but only those related to the reception, processing and output of information, i.e. functions that lend themselves to the logical elaboration all other, infinitely diverse functions of the human brain remain out of sight of AI.

Second, from the point of view of modelling theory, it makes no sense at all to talk about the full identity of the model and the original.

The identification of human and "machine" reason occurs when the subject of thought is replaced by some material system capable of reflecting. The only object of thought is man, armed with all the means at his disposal at a given level of his development. These tools include cybernetic machines that materialize the results of human labor. And, like any manufacturing instrument, AI continues to enhance the capabilities of the human brain. Thinking as a spiritual production, the creation of scientific concepts, theories, ideas, which reflect the laws of the objective world, will remain with one person. Until now, the understanding of thinking has been based mainly on generalized data on psychology, physiology, and linguistics. These AIs allow the question to be asked for a more specific understanding of thinking. AI is not intended to "replace" the person or to "replace" his thinking. It just gives new arguments in favor of the idea of a machine as a human assistant. There is sometimes a statement that cybernetic modelling is generally inapplicable for the study of thinking, because modelling is based on the concepts of correspondence and isomorphism, and thinking is a purely human ability that's supposedly indescribable based on the concepts of correspondence. It is sometimes said that understanding cognition, thinking as the correspondence of an image with an object, means nothing less than a dualistic point of view, which externally compares the object and the image.

Understanding consciousness is a reflection of what inevitably means understanding it as correspondence that arises during the organism's adaptation to the middle. Moreover, this correspondence is not simply the external correspondence of the item and the image as an independent ideal object in relation to the item. This would indeed be a dualistic view, but it could not monopolize the concept of correspondence, just as the correspondence of certain states of the brain to certain states of the outside world. It is this correspondence that carries information about the outside world. The above statement does not distinguish between modelling information on information processes and modelling information on non-informative processes. The information model of the device will not work, but will only simulate the work, however, in terms of thinking, this thesis seems to be controversial. In terms of information processes, their modelling is functionally complete.

Dangers arising during the operation of artificial intelligence

Many of the controversies about the problem of "cybernetics and thinking" are with an emotional background. Recognizing the possibility of AI seems to be something that degrades human dignity. However, questions about the possibility of AI should not be confused with the question of the development and improvement of the human mind. Of course, AI can be used for inappropriate purposes, but this is not a scientific problem, but a moral and ethical one. However, the development of AI raises a number of issues that still need a lot of attention. These problems are related to the dangers that arise during the work of AI. The first problem concerns the possible loss of incentives for creative work as a result of mass computerization or the use of machines in the arts. However, it has recently become clear that a person will not voluntarily give up the most skilled creative work because he is attracted to the person himself. The second problem is of a more serious nature and it has been repeatedly pointed out by specialists such as N. Wiener, N. Amosov, I. Poletaev and others. It consists of the following. There are already machines and programs capable of self-learning in the work process, i.e. to increase the efficiency of adaptation to external factors. In the future, it is possible to have machines with such a level of adaptability and reliability that the need for a person to intervene in the process will disappear. There is a possible degradation of the person's ability to respond to changes in external conditions and, eventually, the inability to take control of himself in the event of an emergency. The question arises about the advisability of introducing a certain border level in the automation of the processes related to difficult emergency situations. In this case, the person supervising the control machine will always have enough skill and reaction to influence the situation in this way, to extinguish the state of emergency. Such situations are possible in transport, in nuclear energy.

Business Law in the Reality of AI

The current business reality in the context of business law (real estate property rights), which are specifically designed to successfully motivate new investments in creating new knowledge and a state with/of fair competition, are still relevant. These two approaches must be mutually exclusive. It is important to draw a red line between the need to maintain active data channels and their flows, on the one side, and to block them on the other, to prevent demotivation, and thus to destroy the incentives to create new knowledge. Currently, the main problem and main difficulty for all AI offices is the lack of development skills for applications based on AI, as well as the number of experts with qualifications and knowledge, which is quite insufficient. The activity of AI systems depends on the absorbed data (and algorithms), so an open access policy is accepted for the registration of intellectual property rights in patents, trademarks and industrial models. This helps small AI companies, as they have an upgrade core and access to this data is evolving. Such problematic situations require overcoming and more adequate attention to cooperation and coordination. The World Intellectual Property Organization ([WIPO wipo.int/pct/en/](http://wipo.int/pct/en/)) has opened a debate on AI issues, with a special focus on the use of AI in the administration of intellectual property rights. The question of how artificial intelligence will be able to replace AI categories and concepts on its own is also relevant, especially when less effort is being put into multilateral rule-making activities than ever before. All of this poses a relevant AI problem, as the area itself typically needs a solution, as AI is a global phenomenon, so patent-sharing technologies and data are certainly global in nature. Patents are only in one branch of law and cover only one jurisdiction. This is a challenge to find a global solution that will offer a realistic ability to collaborate between different systems based on common system standards. Legislation is in relation to the author and

intellectual property law (people only), while in law, computers, computer programs and other forms of expression of AI are not authors and inventors (AI is not considered a separate entity). International practice is accompanied by the concept - the works are protected by copyright because the originality comes to the fore thanks to the creative and intellectual activities of the author (the so-called "personal touch" concept). AI is realized in the activity according to an algorithm where new works are expressed based on their elaboration and analysis. In order to ensure legal protection of a work, it is necessary to establish conditions for accurate and concrete locating of the "dose" of originality in the recently created work. It is relevant what is being discussed, negotiated, a solution is being sought is the realization of the legal protection of what constitutes material for learning, study, analysis, what arouses, arouses interest, some feelings, thoughts and the fig. created with artificial intelligence are the author and originality of the works.

In international practice, there are approaches, i.e. views for concretizing the author of works realized by AI:

1. Author - developer of AI (program or computer code);
2. Author - user of AI (for certain types of programs);
3. The author is directly AI (concept of "electronic person").

The first two approaches are the most common and accepted but do not correspond at all to the key feature of the works as objects of intellectual property - the presence of human creative and intellectual activity. However, the final balance of the actions of the intellectual and creative activity of the person who developed the AI will be without the mediation of such AI, in the form of a program or computer code. With this, the creative activity of the investor is brought to an end.

The result, a product of work created with AI, has virtually no power to act on the AI developer because it is realized on the basis of an algorithm, so the recognition of the person who invested as the author of the products/results of work (works) created by AI is not in accordance with the applicable law, i.e. is not interdependent with the foundations of intellectual property rights.¹³

Normally, all developments that benefit from the development of AI works must first develop a specific computer program with absorbed data, information, materials, or a configuration of the formulated thought that will be presented as a necessary solution (difficult qualify as creative or intellectual activities).

The United Kingdom, India, and New Zealand legally state that the authors of AI-generated works

³ Annemarie Bridy, (2012). Coding Creativity: Copyright and the Artificially Intelligent Author, 5 Stan. Tech. L. ev. 1, 52.

Brady, supra note 2, at 50–52;

Timothy L. Butler, (1982) Can a Computer Be an Author -Copyright Aspects of Artificial Intelligence, 4 Com/ Ent L.S. 707, 739–42;

Ralph D. Clifford, (1996) Intellectual Property in the Era of the Creative Computer Program: Will the True Creator Please Stand up, 71 Tul. L. Rev. 1675, 1685–86, 1694–95;

Evan H. Farr, (1989) Copyright ability of Computer-Created Works, 15 Rutgers Computer & Tech. L.J. 63, 79;

Dane E. Johnson, (2008) Statute of Anne-Imals: Should Cop. Protect Sentient Non-Human Creators, 15 Animal L.15, 19;

Karl F. Milde, Jr., Can a Computer Be an "Author" or an "Inventor"?, 51 J. PAT. OFF. Soc'y 378, 392–95 (1969);

Arthur R. Miller, (1993) Copyright Protection for Computer Programs, Databases, and Computer-Generated Works: Is Anything New Since Cont.?, Harv L. REV. 977, 1056–72;

William T. Ralston, (2004) Copyright in Computer-Composed Music: Hal Meets Handel, 52 J. Copy. Soc'y USA. 281, 302;

Pamela Samuelson, (1989) Allocating Ownership Rights in Computer-Generated Works, 47 U. Pitt. L. Rev. 1185, 1192;

Andrew J. Wu, From Video Games to Artificial Intelligence: Assigning Copyright Ownership to Works Generated by Increasingly Sophisticated Computer Programs, (1997) 25 Aipla Q. J. 131, 155–57

are the people who used the program to create the work. Intellectual property scientists have enriched the terminology with the concept of "electronic personality". Electronic person - a legal entity, which will allow him to be recognized as a subject of legal relations (author of works or inventor).

4. Conclusion

The understanding and thinking for this problem are that current society requires is a big strict attitude to the principles to understand the ascertainment of properties after which will be assessed the ability as reciprocity of/with intelligence. This is everything that is necessary for the realization of understanding of the ultimate goal for lifelong learning and success. Thinking is the highest level of human knowledge of reality. The senses are the only channels for communication of the body with the outside world, and information through them enters the brain. The content of information processes the brain. The most complex (logical) form of information processing is an activity of thinking. The solving mental tasks which life puts them in front of a person, at that moment he begins thinking's, draws conclusions and with that learns the essence of things and phenomena, reveals the laws to connect them and then based on that transforms the world. Thinking not only which is closely related to sensations and perceptions, but it is formed based on them. The rapid increase of the flow of processed information also will lead to significant changes in methods of work and requires automation and intellectualization. Man as an individual, but also people as communities' non-stop will seek a solution to the problem of artificial intelligence, i.e. were constantly and will be in a real situation of facing. It's a hard situation for the same reason what copyright has always been difficult - from all of us we will be required to bring objective legal judgments for the ultimate subjectivity of people: esthetics. Putting on a computer somewhere along the path from brain to „brain“ wears some of these difficulties which are obvious, but that does not change the nature of the issue. They are gone characteristic ideological problems with computer-generated works because all works are computer-generated - or at least maybe they were, which is close enough.

Artificial intelligence is crucial for the mass digital transformation of the current industrial revolution and has the potential to have a significant impact on many areas of life (Kemp, 2016 p.24). Legal support of artificial intelligence should be constantly evolving (intensive), taking her considering the preliminary study for all risks that can be assumed at the current stage of technology development and specifics of use of artificial intelligence in different spheres of life. At the same time, from essential meaning, is to provide a balance between interests of society and individual including and security and the need for progress of innovation in the interest of society.

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